

Figure S1: Map illustrating the year and states for each pea aphid sampling in this study.

A) *Hamiltonella*

B) *Regiella*

C) *Rickettsia*

<u>Locale</u>	<u>Scale/sample size *</u>
New York	10 isolates
 1 isolate	

*Drawn to scale in each panel

Figure S3: Haplotype networks for symbionts of clover-derived aphids.

Figure S4: Maximum likelihood phylogeny for *Serratia*, based on concatenated alignment of *gyrB* & *hrpA* gene sequences.

Figure S5: Maximum likelihood phylogeny for *Spiroplasma*, based on concatenated alignment of *rpoB* & *dnaA* gene sequences.

Host-race associated differentiation & recombination among *Regiella*

Figure S6: *Regiella* strain differences among the alfalfa vs. clover pea aphid host races.

Figure S7: Maximum likelihood phylogeny for *Rickettsia*, based on *gltA* gene sequences.

Figure S8: Maximum likelihood phylogeny for *Hamiltonella*, based on concatenated alignment of eight loci.

A. No detected strain variation shaping *Serratia-Rickettsia* co-infection

B. Alfalfa-specific strain variation shaping *Rickettsia-Serratia* co-infection

Figure S9: Strain composition across a variably enriched species-level co-infection - *Serratia* & *Rickettsia*.

A. No detected strain variation shaping *Hamiltonella's Serratia* avoidance

B. No detected strain variation shaping *Serratia's Hamiltonella* avoidance

A.

Figure S10: Strain composition across a rare species-level co-infection - *Hamiltonella* & *Serratia*.

A. Host race-confounded strain variation: *Regiella* v. *Rickettsia* avoidance

Data pooled across host races

	Reg-A pooled	Reg-B pooled	Rec-C pooled	Reg-D pooled
Rick-	57	45	2	1
Rick+	3	24	0	0

p < 1e-04***

B. No clear strain variation shaping *Rickettsia*'s *Regiella* avoidance

Figure S11: Strain composition across a rare species-level co-infection - *Regiella* & *Rickettsia*.

Minimal strain variation shaping *Hamiltonella's* *Rickettsiella* avoidance

Figure S12: *Hamiltonella* strain composition across a rare species-level co-infection - *Hamiltonella* & *Rickettsiella*.

A. *Hamiltonella* strains B & A enriched for *Rickettsia* association in 1-2 host races

B. *Rickettsia* strain B lives with *Hamiltonella* in nearly all instances

C. Asymmetrical specificity of *Rickettsia* strain B with *Hamiltonella* strain B on alfalfa

Figure S13: Strain composition across an enriched species-level co-infection - *Hamiltonella* & *Rickettsia*.

A. *Hamiltonella* strain B enriched for *Spiroplasma* co-infection on alfalfa

B. *Spiroplasma* strain B enriched for *Hamiltonella* co-infection

C. Bidirectional specificity between *Spiroplasma* strain B and *Hamiltonella* strain B on alfalfa

D. Bi-directional specificity between *Hamiltonella* B sub-strain I and *Spiroplasma* B

Figure S14: Strain composition across a newly enriched species-level co-infection - *Hamiltonella* & *Spiroplasma*.

Facultative symbiont co-infections

Compounds 'expanded' (synthesized) by facultative symbionts within the metabolic background provided by pea aphids & *Buchnera*

- By one or both co-infecting symbionts
- By one or both co-infecting symbionts, but variable among *Hamiltonella* strains
- Synergistic expansion requiring both facultative symbionts
- Compound not 'expanded' by either (or both) symbiont(s)

Figure S16: Compounds expanded by facultative symbionts, within the metabolic context of the pea aphid + *Buchnera* environment.

Expanded by facultative symbionts

- C19673: all but *Regiella*
- C19845: all but *Rickettsiella* & *Regiella*
- *C1092: all but *Serratia*, *Rickettsiella*, & *Regiella*; ***Ser-Rcl synergistically***
- *C1037: all but *Serratia*, *Rickettsiella*, & *Regiella*; ***Ser-Rcl synergistically***
- *C22458: all but *Serratia*, *Rickettsiella*, & *Regiella*; ***Ser-Rcl synergistically***
- C00086: only *Rickettsiella*

Buchnera-expanded

- C20373: all isolates
- C20374: Tuc7 & 5A
- C20375: Tuc7 & 5A
- C20377: all isolates
- C20378: Tuc7 & 5A
- C19846: Tuc7 & 5A
- C01909: all isolates

Host-expanded

- C19673
- C20376
- C05921
- C05552
- C06250

Not expanded

- C01209
- C20683
- C2656
- C1063
- *C00120 – *Buchnera* seem to encode this, as do most facultative symbionts
- C20387
- C20386
- C20384
- C20385
- C01894
- C00047

Figure S17: KEGG pathway map for biotin metabolism illustrating compounds 'expanded' within the pea aphid holobiont, and the organisms (hosts vs. symbionts) responsible for expansion.

Figure S18: Mapping gene-inactivating mutations onto the respective phylogenies of three biotin synthesizing pseudogenes in *Serratia symbiotica*.

A. Synergistically expanded peptidoglycan metabolism

B. Top BLASTp hits for proteins expanding joint *Serratia-Rickettsiella* metabolism

Step # in figure	EC number	Encoding bacterium	BLASTp results			
			Enzymes names for BLAST hits	Accession #	Organism	% identity
1	2.7.1.193	<i>Serratia symbiotica</i>	N-acetylglucosamine-specific PTS transporter subunit IIBC/PTS N-acetyl glucosamine transporter subunit IIABC	WP_040264861.1	<i>Serratia symbiotica</i>	99.85%
2	4.2.1.126	<i>Serratia symbiotica</i>	N-acetylmuramic acid 6-phosphate etherase	WP_040266569.1	<i>Serratia symbiotica</i>	98.65%
3	EC 3.1.3.105	<i>Rickettsiella viridis</i>	phosphoglycolate phosphatase/HAD family hydrolase/HAD-IA family hydrolase	WP_218813822.1	<i>Rickettsiella</i> endosymbiont of <i>Dermanyssus gallinae</i>	86.67%
4	EC 2.7.1.221	<i>Rickettsiella viridis</i>	phosphotransferase/aminoglycoside phosphotransferase/	WP_218814306.1	<i>Rickettsiella</i> endosymbiont of <i>Dermanyssus gallinae</i>	90.96%
5	EC 2.7.7.99	<i>Rickettsiella viridis</i>	nucleotidyltransferase family protein	WP_246562478.1	<i>Rickettsiella</i> endosymbiont of <i>Dermanyssus gallinae</i>	93.40%

C. 2nd non-redundant BLASTp hits - proteins expanding *Ser-Rcl* metabolism

Step # in figure	EC number	Encoding bacterium	BLASTp results			
			Enzymes names for BLAST hits	Accession #	Organism	% identity
1	2.7.1.193	<i>Serratia symbiotica</i>	N-acetylglucosamine-specific PTS transporter subunit IIBC/PTS N-acetyl glucosamine transporter subunit IIABC	QD112731.1	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	87.46%
2	4.2.1.126	<i>Serratia symbiotica</i>	N-acetylmuramic acid 6-phosphate etherase	WP_033644118.1	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	90.17%
3	EC 3.1.3.105	<i>Rickettsiella viridis</i>	phosphoglycolate phosphatase/HAD family hydrolase/HAD-IA family hydrolase	RDH40634.1	<i>Candidatus Aquirickettsiella gammari</i>	61.19%
4	EC 2.7.1.221	<i>Rickettsiella viridis</i>	phosphotransferase/aminoglycoside phosphotransferase/	RDH39911.1	<i>Candidatus Aquirickettsiella gammari</i>	65.85%
5	EC 2.7.7.99	<i>Rickettsiella viridis</i>	nucleotidyltransferase family protein	RDH39910.1	<i>Candidatus Aquirickettsiella gammari</i>	66.67%

Figure S19: Expanded metabolism realized under *Serratia-Rickettsiella* co-infection supports peptidoglycan biosynthesis.

Hamiltonella A

with vs. without Spiroplasma

Hamiltonella B

with vs. without Spiroplasma

Figure S20: Elevations in *Hamiltonella* strain B-*Spiroplasma* co-infection appear ephemeral, and geographically confined. Rarity of *Hamiltonella* A-*Spiroplasma* co-infections appears consistent.

Hamiltonella A

with vs. without *Fukatsuia*

Hamiltonella B

with vs. without *Fukatsuia*

Figure S21: *Hamiltonella* strain B co-infection enrichment with *Fukatsuia* appears consistent over time and space, as does the rarity of *Hamiltonella A-Fukatsuia* co-infection.

Hamiltonella C

with vs. without Regiella

Hamiltonella B

with vs. without Regiella

Figure S22: *Hamiltonella* strain C co-infection enrichment with *Regiella* appears geographically and temporally stable, as does the rarity of *Hamiltonella B*-*Regiella* co-infection.